

A Kinetic Study of Oxidation of Isobutyl Alcohol with Aqueous Iodine

(Km.) ANITA MANGLIK and S. K. SHARMA*

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Meerut-250 002

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Oxidation of isobutyl alcohol with aqueous iodine has been studied at constant pH (9.18). The reaction is zero and first order with respect to iodine and substrate respectively. The reaction is base catalysed and is found dependent on the first power of OH⁻ ion concentration. The influence of various factors i.e. ionic strength, pH, dielectric constant, D₂O and temperature on the reaction rate have been studied and hydride abstraction mechanism has been suggested for the reaction.

OXIDATION of alcohols by halogens particularly by chlorine and bromine have been studied by various workers¹⁻⁴. Two types of mechanism have been suggested. Ester mechanism was suggested for the reaction of isopropyl alcohol and bromine⁵ or chlorine⁶. Kaplan⁷ and Banerjee⁸ suggested hydride abstraction mechanism for the oxidation of alcohols. The oxidation of benzhydrols by iodine in alkaline medium (non-aqueous) has been reported by Ogata and Nagura⁹.

However, earlier studies were conducted mainly in the acid medium. In alkaline aqueous medium halogens are mostly converted to inert hypohalite anion¹⁰, due to which oxidising conditions may change. In the present paper results of investigation on oxidation of isobutylalcohol with aqueous iodine in alkaline medium are reported.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade. Double distilled water was used in preparing all solutions. Stock iodine solution was prepared by dissolving iodine in aqueous solution of potassium iodide. The reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.2 M$) using sodium perchlorate. Borax solution was used to maintain constant pH of 9.18. To avoid photochemical effects, reaction bottles, blackened from outside were used and were suspended in thermostat for at least 30 min before starting the reaction. The reaction was monitored by estimating the unreacted iodine at various intervals of time by standard hypo solution. Suitable quantity of potassium iodide was added to avoid simultaneous hydrolysis of iodine during the reaction. Kinetic measurements are reproducible within 1% error.

Product analysis: The stoichiometry shows that 1 mole of isobutyl alcohol reacts with 1 mole of iodine to give isobutyraldehyde which was identified from the reaction mixture by precipitation

of its 2, 4-DNP derivative and spot test¹¹. The end product was identified to be isobutyric acid.

Results and Discussion

Out of the four species I₂, HOI, H₂OI⁺ and I₃⁻ which may be existing in the aqueous iodine solution, iodine acts as an oxidising agent¹². In the large concentration of alcohol the order of reaction has been found to be zero as indicated by the constancy of x/t or by the linear plot of x vs t passing through origin (x is the number of moles of iodine consumed in time t). By varying the concentration of alcohol or iodine the rate was found to depend on the first power of alcohol concentration and independent of iodine concentration (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF OXIDATION RATE ON THE CONCENTRATION OF ISOBUTYL ALCOHOL AT 35°

[KI]=0.06 M; $\mu=0.20$, pH=9.18

[I ₂] × 10 ⁴ M	5.0	15.0	40.0	60.00	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
[Alc] × M	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.02	0.20	0.30	0.40
k × 10 ⁶ M sec ⁻¹	2.12	2.09	2.09	2.09	0.41	4.07	6.18	8.39
k' × 10 ⁷ / [Alc] sec ⁻¹	2.12	2.09	2.09	2.09	2.05	2.03	2.06	2.07

The plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[ROH] at 35° is linear with no intercept on the axis. This shows the absence of a preformed complex or complex whose formation constant is too low to be kinetically determined. The reaction was found to be base catalysed. The initial rate¹³ of the reaction was determined in the presence of varying concentrations of OH⁻ ions. Since NaOH and I₂ also react simultaneously, the initial rate for this reaction was also determined separately under similar conditions. Thus the first order rate constant with respect to OH⁻ ions was calculated (Table 2). The rate equation can be written as

$$-\frac{d[I_2]}{dt} = k [Alc] [OH^-]$$

*For correspondence.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF OXIDATION RATE ON THE CONCENTRATION OF OH⁻ IONS AT 35°

[I₂]=0.001 M, [Alc]=0.05 M; [KI]=0.06 M, μ=0.2 M

[NaOH] M	Initial rate with alcohol k _o ' × 10 ⁸ M sec ⁻¹	Initial rate without alcohol k _o ' × 10 ⁸ M sec ⁻¹	(k _o ' - k _o ') = k _o × 10 ⁸ M sec ⁻¹	$\frac{k_o \times 10^8}{[OH^-]}$ sec ⁻¹
0.004	3.66	3.30	3.6	9.00
0.005	4.14	3.70	4.4	8.80
0.006	4.44	3.92	5.2	8.66
0.007	4.74	4.12	6.2	8.55
0.008	4.96	4.26	7.0	8.75

When the concentration of NaClO₄ was varied (0.05 M to 0.5 M), the rate of the reaction was found to remain almost constant indicating that either two molecules or a molecule and ion are involved in the reaction. This fact was further confirmed by studying the reaction in varying concentrations of dioxan and water (v/v). The rate was found to increase with the decrease in dielectric constant (Table 3) showing that reaction was taking place between ion and molecule¹⁴.

TABLE 3—ISOBUTYL ALCOHOL AND AQUEOUS IODINE IN DIOXAN-WATER AT 25°

[Alc]=0.1 M, [I₂]=0.001 M [KI]=0.06 M μ=0.2 M pH=9.18

% Dioxan	0	5	10	20	30	35
Dielectric constant	78.5	74.9	71.2	62.2	53.5	48.8
k × 10 ⁷ , M sec ⁻¹	1.04	1.83	3.16	4.16	9.16	12.50

Effect of iodide ions: Effect of iodide ions on the reaction rate was studied by the addition of varying concentration of KI and cadmium iodide. The rate was found to decrease with the increase in the concentration of iodide ions, showing the formation of iodide ions in the reaction equilibrium.

Isotope effect: The rate k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} at 35° has been determined to be 1.67 indicating the possibility of deprotonation¹⁵ of isobutyl alcohol in the rate determining step.

Effect of temperature: Activation parameters were calculated from the different values of rate constants obtained at different temperatures by usual methods (Table 4).

TABLE 4

E _a k.cal/mol	ΔH [‡] k.cal/mol	ΔS [‡] e.u.	ΔG [‡] k.cal		
12.55 ± 0.17	12.09 ± 0.44	-54.63 ± 0.04	28.8 ± 0.38		
Temp, °C	25	30	35	40	45
k × 10 ⁸ , M sec ⁻¹	1.04	1.57	2.08	3.15	4.18

For simple ion-dipole interactions, the principal contribution of ΔG[‡] is the increase in free energy arising from the distribution of charge over a large ion X in the transition state. On such basis ion

dipole reaction should be accelerated in solvents of decreasing dielectric constant (Table 3). Thus, large positive value of ΔG[‡] is in confirmation with the nature of reaction. High negative value of entropy is due to the influence of charge in the initial state of reactants and final state of the activated complex along with induced dipole forces.

Effect of pH change: Borate buffers were used to study the effect of change of pH. The rate was found to increase with increase in pH value (Table 5).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF pH VARIATION ON THE REACTION RATE AT 25°

[I₂]=0.0008 M, [Alc]=0.10 M, [KI]=0.01 M, μ=0.2 M

pH	7.25	8.17	9.2	9.79
k' × 10 ⁷ , sec ⁻¹	0.92	1.48	4.89	9.8

Aqueous alcohols are found to exist in the following equilibrium:

With the increase in pH, the above equilibrium shifts towards the right increasing the concentration of RO⁻ ions in the solution. It has been shown^{16,17} that alkoxide ions are more easily oxidised than their molecular form. Iodine being a weaker oxidising agent than chlorine and bromine seems to have little tendency to attack molecular form which is indicated in the study of pH rate profile. Since the rate is found to depend on the concentration of alcohol (Table 1) and not on the iodine concentration, the increase in the rate with increase in the pH value may be due to the increase in the concentration of alkoxide ions.

Alkoxide ions are good hydride donor¹⁷ as α-hydrogen on them may easily be removed due to the tendency of the negatively charged oxygen atom to form a double bond with carbon. Also the reaction of halogens with negatively charged ions are more likely than with undissociated molecules owing to the strong electron attracting character of the halogens¹⁸.

Thus on the basis of above facts following mechanism can be proposed:

All subsequent steps leading to the formation of acid are considered to be fast. This assumption has been verified by determining the rate of oxidation of isobutyraldehyde under similar conditions of experiment which is found to be 370 times faster than the rate for oxidation by alcohol.

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